

METHODS OF FORMING SPIRITUAL AND MORAL CULTURE OF
YOUTH IN THE NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: In this article, the methods of forming the spiritual and moral culture of young people in the new Uzbekistan, the main subject of art and ethics is man, if art reflects the goals and interests of a person, opinions, feelings, inner experiences, Morality is embedded in the core of human social relations and relationships, and it is explained that morality is necessary in life and society.

Key words and phrases: sports, folk traditional values, intercultural relations, practical skills, continuous education, individual qualities, economic development, educational standards, education and training, scientific-methodical, subjective innovation in students.

When it comes to the relationship between art and morality, it should be noted that they have a close relationship like flesh and nails. Because in every real work of art, the struggle between good and evil is perceived as the main conflict, virtues such as humanity, truthfulness, correctness, justice, love, loyalty are glorified, fate, death and dying. Issues such as life, the meaning of life, and the pursuit of happiness are thrown into the middle. The problem of moral ideal is the crown of every artistic work. For example, Alisher Navoi's Farhodi, Shirin, Shakespeare's Romeo, Juliet, Aybek's Navoi are moral ideals in the works of these authors. It is impossible to imagine the works of Navoi, Shakespeare and Oibek without them.

The second approach is the method of "freeing" art from morality. This approach, which first arose during the decline of the ancient world, became an independent sophisticated current in the bosom of developed capitalist society in Europe. At the beginning, the "immoral" approach to art arises in the form of protest against the spirit of European bourgeois consumerism, that is, in the spirit of struggle against subordinating art to the rules of morality and etiquette of the ruling circles. This situation is reflected in the works of artists such as Oscar Wilde, Edgar Poe, Baudelaire. From the end of the 19th century, openly aesthetic immorality began to be widely promoted. For example, the German philosopher F. Nietzsche said that the spirit of morality stifles the freedom of art, and art should be excluded from both virtue and literature. The third approach is the method of combining morality and "immorality" in art. This method was

first theoretically based by Aristotle. Later it settled in the style of a revolutionary democratic movement. In the essence of this style of artistic creation, there is a high appreciation of the moral and educational importance of art, in which the moral principle is not the function of an external shell in relation to the aesthetic dream, but rather its inner structural core. According to this approach, art serves as an aesthetic school of morality, and if works of art lack artistry, they are devoid of morality. In other words, artistry always requires morality, and morality requires a high level of refined taste.

In fact, the following can be included in the factors that make up spiritual education and moral education and illuminate its essence: a) ethics and manners; b) the knowledge, science, practical skills, talent, abilities that have arisen in the course of practical work; c) faith, belief, conscience, honesty, sincerity, which is the result of moral and scientific maturity; g) is a worldview and ideology aimed at summarizing human knowledge and practical experience.

Spiritual and moral education is considered the strength of the nation and society, and it is always getting richer. Spiritual culture is a unique socio-historical phenomenon that belongs to every nation and has deep historical roots. The independence of our republic created important conditions and opportunities for the formation of spiritual education among students. Students are developing a sense of national identity, belonging to the nation and its history.

It is appropriate to pay attention to the harmonious development of mental and spiritual aspects of a person in the formation of spiritual and moral education in students. The priority of mental and spiritual ability leads to the formation of spiritual culture in students at the expected level. After all, spiritual education is an important criterion of moral maturity of students. Spiritual culture requires all-round development of students and young people, formation of national spirit and general social education.

In conclusion, it should be said that it is necessary to admit that in our most recent history, in many countries of the world, foreign ideas are deliberately inculcated in the minds of young people, de-idealizing societies, encouraging the representatives of the new generation to be indifferent, not to patriotism, to playfulness. we have witnessed that movements have taken root. In this, the main attention was focused on distancing young people from national values and teaching them to think lightly. Unfortunately, this process did not bypass Uzbekistan. Today, it is true that some of our young people glorify other cultures

and values. But we need to understand that this means that the bell of crisis is ringing for the future.

The main subject of art and ethics is man. If art reflects human goals and interests, opinions, feelings, and inner experiences, morality is absorbed into the core of human social relations and relationships. In life, in ordinary society, there is no incident that is not related to morality. Human relations and behavior serve as the direct object of morality. Since ancient times, art has developed in close connection with religion. Since ancient times, art and religion have formed a doctrinal unity. Art and religion belong to the ranks of spiritual and practical forms of social consciousness, and both of them take place from the "upper floor" of the ideological superstructure above the economic ground.

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